

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19106643

Information Sharing and Organizational Innovativeness of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research examined the relationship between Information Sharing and Organisational Innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The researcher selected all the twenty deposit money banks with main branch in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State as population for the study. The work was therefore a census study since the population of twenty deposit money banks was a manageable size. The researcher purposively selected five managerial staff from each of the twenty deposit money banks making a total of one hundred staff as respondents. The researcher used both the primary and secondary data in the course of this study. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistic was the bivariate statistic adopted to test the ten formulated hypotheses. The outcome of the study revealed that information sharing is positively and significantly related with organisational innovativeness. It was therefore concluded that adequate information sharing by bank managers improves both product, process and service innovativeness thereby promoting growth and expansion of deposit money banks in Nigeria through innovativeness. It was then recommended that deposit money banks should as a matter of necessity engage in managerial empowerment practices such as information sharing, competence acquisition and full grant of work discretion as a means of improving organisational innovativeness. Management of deposit money banks should engage highly motivated and empowered managers in order to initiate and sustain organisational innovativeness through product, process and service innovativeness. Management of deposit money banks should inculcate proper information sharing channels among their employees to guarantee product, process and service effectiveness through innovative decision and actions.

Keywords: Information Sharing, Organizational Innovativeness, Product, Process and Service innovativeness

1. INTRODUCTION

It has been observed that following the increased findings in the literature that support a positive relationship between managerial empowerment and organisational innovativeness, it is pertinent that failure to inculcate empowerment culture through engaging in empowerment behaviours may negatively affect the innovativeness and productivity performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria (Ottih, 2016). These negative effect may however include reputation and image problem; loss of value; loss of relevance; loss of competitive position; customers' dissatisfaction; low market share; obsolescence; low quality or substandard services; low employees motivation, morale and commitment; high employees turnover; low profits or returns on investment; low productivity. It was also observed that most of these firms over the years have not really undergone repackaging or innovative or creativity method of learning and are still operating with the out-dated methods in this time of increased competition in the industry

while others have employed different techniques, skills, competence and talents in their mode of operation to be able to cope with the demands of the industry. However, in a dynamic external environment, adaptable organisations are more likely to survive and thrive than mechanistic organisations (Burns & Stalker 1961). Adaptability often takes the form of innovation, the invention or adoption of processes, practices, products, and services by an organization which is a challenge (Becker & Mathieu, 2003).

Organizational innovation refers to creative destruction. It consists of abandoning and surpassing a traditional model and creates something new that is generally positive (Moudden & Balhadj, 2024). Innovativeness can be defined as the capacity of accomplishing a successful introduction, into a real situation that are new to a particular situation in question. In the same vein, innovativeness is universally perceived as exploring something new that has not existed before. On the other hand, innovativeness can be viewed as the degree of adoption (sooner or later) of new ideas by an individual related to the other members of the system (Faco et al., 2020). Innovation is the successful exploitation of new ideas: it is a profitable outcome of the creative process, which involves generating and applying in a specific context products, services, procedures and processes that are desirable and viable (Dimnwobi, et al., 2016). Naturally, people who create and people who innovate can have different attributes and perspectives. More so, innovation on the other hand usually implies the use of these ideas. On the other hand, there are several studies conducted alongside this variable, however, this study would examine the relationship between information sharing and organizational innovativeness.

Information sharing can be viewed or defined as one-to-one exchanges of data between a sender and receiver. Hence, information sharing has a long history in academic literature (Pala, & Zhuang, 2019). information sharing can be understood as ‘a set of activities by which information is provided to others, either proactively or upon request, such that the information has an impact on another person's (or persons) image of the world and creates a shared, or mutually compatible working, understanding of the world. Hence, the process of information sharing incorporates two major aspects, i.e., giving information to others, and receiving information that has been provided by the information giver. In same vein, define knowledge as ‘information processed by individuals including ideas, facts, expertise, and judgments relevant for individual, team, and organizational performance. Nevertheless, information sharing describes a single, one-directional activity. Thus, all researchers do not approach information sharing as a generic concept incorporating the aspects of giving and receiving of information as explained by Raijo (2017), that is to say, information sharing may also be understood as one-way communication, that is, information giving only. Therefore, the need to adopt information sharing in deposit money banks in Nigeria as a strategic tool and managerial practice in order to expand and enhance innovativeness is why the researcher seeks to examine the relationship between the variables.

1.1. Purpose and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between information sharing and organisational innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

- i. To assess the relationship between information sharing and product innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- ii. To assess the relationship between information sharing and process innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- iii. To assess the relationship between information sharing and service innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.1: Conceptual framework depicting the relationship between information sharing and organizational innovativeness

Source: Desk Research (2026); Bowen & Lawler (1992, 1995); Balachandran, and Thomas (2007).

1.3 Research Questions

Based on the statement of the research problem, aim of the study and its objectives, this study poses the following questions to guide the researcher, thus:

1. What is the relationship between information sharing and product innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between information sharing and process innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between information sharing and service innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria?

1.4 Statement of Hypotheses

Based on the foregoing arguments, the following hypotheses were formulated to direct the study;

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between information sharing and product innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between information sharing and process innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between information sharing and service innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Achievement Motivation Theory

The underpinning baseline theory this study is the achievement motivation theory. This theory was propounded by a behavioural scientist, David C. McClelland in the year 1961. He held the view that achievement motivation is the most important single trait that separates entrepreneurs from non-entrepreneurs. McClelland (1985) in his needs theory proposed that there are three major needs or motives in every work situation such as: need for achievement, need for power, and need for affiliation. The need for achievement is the drive to excel in any task, to achieve in relation to a set of standards, and to strive to succeed. The need for affiliation is the desire for friendly and close interpersonal relationship at work environments. Consequently, the daily role or responsibilities of university managers towards institutional effectiveness seems to be highly influenced by McClellands (1985) model of needs theory. However, every effective university manager appears to have a high level need for achievement, and moderate level needs for both power and affiliation (Basse & Akpan, 2010). The major underlying principle of this theory is that the needs are largely culturally derived (Okere, 2013). The theory is

relevant to this study because, the family backgrounds of intra-preneurs play a very important role in their development. It is as a result of this high influence of environmental factors that McClelland asserts that achievement motivation can be developed through training (Ottih, 2016).

2.2 Conceptual Review

Information Sharing

Information sharing can be viewed or defined as the exchange of knowledge, data or insight between employees or individuals, firms, or systems in order to improve decision-making communication or collaboration. That is to say, information sharing is a central process through which team members can actually or collectively utilize their information resources (Gigone & Hastie, 1993). Communicating goals and priorities to employees and offering feedback on performance are practices that have been found to encourage empowerment. Specific and challenging goals in general serve to raise employee motivation and performance (Locke & Latham 1990). Top-down communication that conveys the leadership's priorities and goals can, therefore, encourage achievement-oriented employees to seek new strategies and tactics for attaining those goals. Negative feedback indicative of failure also signals the need to search for new ways of narrowing the performance gap as pointed out by Cyert and March (1963); Fernandez and Wise (2010), thereby encouraging employees to innovate. While goal ambiguity in the public sector can undercut the effectiveness of goal setting as a motivational approach Rainey (2009), at the level of the work team or the individual employee, goals are often sufficiently clear for this empowerment practice to have a positive impact on the extent to which an employee feels encouraged to innovate. Sharing information is a necessary precondition to another important feature found in successful work systems: encouraging the decentralization of decision making and broader employee participation and empowerment in controlling their own processes.

Organizational Innovativeness

The term "innovation" can be defined as the implementation of new, or significantly improved, products (goods or services) or processes or new methods of marketing, organisational practices, work organisation, and establishment of external relations (OECD, 2005). The term organisational innovativeness has been employed in connection with the organizational conditions that enable the innovation to occur. Organisational innovativeness encompasses the organisational dimensions that support the efficient management of internal and external knowledge flows and the tangible and intangible assets that sustain the organisation's capability to innovate in a continuous and long-lasting manner (Quandt et al., 2013). Organisational innovativeness is perceived in contemporary literature as a desirable aspect of organisations because it energizes them and enhances their probability of survival and continued success.

Measures of Organizational Innovativeness

Product Innovativeness

Product innovativeness can be defined as the extent to which the product has achieved novelty, provoked new insights and perspectives, including product advantage, product newness and product line improvement (Jordan & Segelod, 2006). New product development performance referred to the extent to which the new product has achieved its expected performance, including profit margin, return on assets, return on investment, etc. (Brown & Eisenhardt, 1995). According to Brigham and Ehrhardt (2010), financial ratios are intended to aid in evaluating. Product Innovativeness can be defined as new or significantly improved goods and services, which generate value for the final consumer. Product innovativeness is strategically important to service firms.

Process Innovativeness

Process innovation can be viewed as a tool to improve organisational efficiency. A firm may adopt new technologies, buy new machineries, train their employees and re-organize their processes to make a process innovation. Process innovation is the result not only of combining and co-ordinating external resources to gain and internalize new knowledge, but also of legitimizing and conforming to normative standards and pressures. The fundamental premise of institutional theory is that organisational behavior is influenced by societal influences and pressures to conform and thus, underscores how important it is for organisations to enhance their legitimacy. As a result, organisations strive for both economic fitness,

which emphasizes the importance of resources, and social fitness, which stresses the pursuit of legitimacy in the eyes of the stakeholders thereby accentuating the significance of the institutional environment (Grewal & Dharwadkar, 2002). Process innovation refers to the new procedures, policies, organisational forms and knowledge embodied in the distribution channels, products, applications, as well as customer expectations, preferences, and needs (Gupta, 2013).

Service Innovativeness

Service innovation can be viewed or referred to as innovation taking place in the various contexts of services, including the introduction of new services or incremental improvements of existing services. Service innovation can provide an effective way to create sustained competitive advantage for a company. Turning to or assuming service strategies may help organisations to overcome the problem of growth maintenance in saturated markets as well as the problem caused by the circumstance of commoditization (Reinartz & Ulaga, 2008). Firms can benefit from a service-based strategy in many ways. For example, adopting a service-based strategy can help to excel in service offerings, cost structure, delivery system, and technology (Gronroos, 2007). That is to say, services are often highly tailored products to customer needs, and consequently, the traditional product-based innovation view and the measurements it employs for assessing the value of innovations are not suitable for services and the businesses behind.

2.3 Empirical Review

Below are previous studies conducted on the study variables;

A study conducted by Almeahadi et al. (2014) investigated the Effects of Managerial Empowerment Applications on Organisational Creativity and Innovativeness in Enterprises: The Case of Oiz in Turkey. The study adopted a survey technique research design. This study aims to evaluate the effect of managerial empowerment on organisational creativity and innovativeness in Konya Organized Industry. Surveys were given to 52 employees with different titles and positions within the enterprises. Literature review was done and required theoretical infrastructure has been built up. The surveys that are prepared to collect information about managerial empowerment applications, creativity and innovativeness include 4 parts and 54 questions. In the first part, there are 3 questions to identify demographic information of participants. Results show that enterprises which employ managerial empowerment applications increase their organisational creativity and innovativeness at the same time. However, this depends on having a common point of view of managers and other employees in the point of expected aims and benefits.

Another study conducted by Chang and Liu (2008), Titled: Managerial Empowerment, Innovative Behavior And Job Productivity Of Public Health Nurses in Taiwan. The study conducted a cross-sectional research design. The objective of this study was to investigate the relationships between managerial empowerment, innovative behaviours and job productivity of public health nurses (PHNs). Purposive sampling was conducted from six health bureaus in northern Taiwan. 670 PHNs were approached and 576 valid questionnaires were collected, with a response rate of 85.9%. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data by post. The result of the study showed that meaning and competence subscales of psychological empowerment, information and opportunity subscales of organisational empowerment, and innovative behaviours were the predictors of job productivity, only accounting for 16.4% of the variance. The competence subscale of psychological empowerment made the most contribution to job productivity ($b = 0.31$). Meaning subscale of psychological empowerment has a negative impact on job productivity. The study concluded that managerial empowerment and innovative behaviour of PHNs have little influence on job productivity. Employees with greater competence for delivering public health showed higher self-evaluated job productivity. The negative influences on job productivity possibly caused by conflict meaning on public health among PHNs in current public health policy.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quantitative research approach and the correlational research design as it focused on evaluating the relationship between managerial empowerment and organizational innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The population for this study consist of all the deposit money banks licensed to operate in Nigeria. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the number of deposit

money banks in Nigeria with operational permit is twenty two (22). Due to the insecurity nature of some part of the country, not all the deposit money banks were used in the study. The (22) deposit money banks in Nigeria by Okanya, and Paseda (2019) out of which only twenty (20) were operational as at the time of this study with Main Branch in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. However, the two (2) deposit money banks without main branch in Port Harcourt are operational only in Lagos State as at the time of this study. Managerial staff which include Branch Managers, Operations Manager, Human Resource Managers, Customer Relations Managers and Internet Technology Managers as respondents because the researcher wanted to select those who directly deals with employee issues and those who are also involved in formulation and implementation of strategies for managerial empowerment. Also, purposive sampling technique was used to administer the questionnaires to all the respondents. The Pearson Product Movement Correlation was adopted alongside or with the aid of SPSS 21.0 version software package to establish the relationship between predictor variable and the measures of the organizational innovativeness.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Table 1.1: Number of questionnaire produced, distributed, retrieved and used

S/N	Questionnaire	QTY	%
1	Numbers of copies produced	100	100
2	Numbers of copies distributed	100	100
3	Numbers of copies retrieved	100	100
4	Numbers of copies used	100	100

Source: Survey Data, 2026.

Univariate Analyses

The presentation of the response rate of individual study begins with the predictor variable and dimensions of managerial empowerment, such as information sharing and it then proceeds to the criterion variable (organizational innovativeness, and measures such as: product innovativeness, process and service innovativeness. In generating the data on the operationalized variables, the study used a 5-point Likert scale instrument.

Bivariate Data Analysis

The bivariate hypothetical statements for the study were tested using the Pearson Product Movement Correlation. The correlation was adopted as the correlation tool as a result of its parametric features (normality of distribution, homogeneity of variance for the variables) and its suitability for data which is either scaled on the interval of scaling. Specifically, the tests covered hypotheses H_{01} to H_{03} which were bivariate at all, stated in the null manner.

Information Sharing and Organizational Innovativeness Measures

The result of correlation matrix obtained for information sharing and organizational innovativeness and its measures (product, process and services innovativeness) of food and beverages firms in South-South, Nigeria. Table 1.2 below shows the result of correlation matrix obtained for information sharing and measures of organizational innovativeness. Also displayed in the table is the statistical test of significance (p - value), which makes us able to answer our research question and generalize our findings to the study population.

Table 1.2 Correlations Matrix for Information Sharing and measures of Organizational Innovativeness

The null hypotheses (Hypothesis 1-3) were tested in this study using the Pearson Product Movement Correlation (PPMC) statistic. The correlation results are presented in the tables below:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between information sharing and product innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 1.2: Information sharing and product innovativeness

		Info_sha	Prod_Inn
Info_sha	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	1	.505*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	Sum of squares and Gross Products	2005.310	939.480
	Covariance	20.256	9.490
	N	100	100
Prod_Inn	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	.505*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Sum of squares and Gross Products	939.480	1711.310
	Covariance	9.490	17.286
	N	100	100

Note: Inf_sha = Information sharing; Prod_Inn = product innovativeness; * = correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

As shown from the data analysis using a sample size of 100 on table 1.2, the relationship between information sharing and product innovativeness is strong, positive and significant. Evidence show that Pearson product correlation coefficient is .505 and the probability value less than the critical value (i.e. $r = .505$, $p = .000 < 0.05$). In other words, information sharing is positively correlated with product innovativeness. This means, if deposit money bank employees increase their level of information sharing, product innovativeness will also increase. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between information sharing and product innovativeness was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between information sharing and product innovativeness was accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between information sharing and process innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 1.3: Information sharing and process innovativeness

		Info_sha	Proc_Inn
Info_sha	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	1	.988**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	Sum of squares and Gross Products	2005.310	373.240
	Covariance	20.256	6.290
	N	100	100
Proc_Inn	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	.988**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Sum of squares and Gross Products	373.240	2005.310
	Covariance	6.290	20.256
	N	100	100

Note: Inf_sha = Information sharing; Proc_Inn = process innovativeness; ** = correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As shown from the data analysis using a sample size of 100 on table 1.3, the relationship between information sharing and process innovativeness is strong, positive and significant. Evidence show that Pearson product correlation coefficient is .988 and the probability value less than the critical value (i.e. $r = .988$, $p = .000 < 0.01$). In other words, information sharing is positively correlated with process innovativeness. This means, if deposit money bank employees strengthens their level of information

sharing, process innovativeness will as well, increase. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between information sharing and process innovativeness was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between information sharing and process innovativeness was accepted.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between information sharing and service innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 1.4: Information sharing and service innovativeness

		Info_sha	Serv_Inn
Info_sha	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	1	.106**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.01
	Sum of squares and Gross Products	2005.310	25.120
	Covariance	20.256	3.117
	N	100	100
Serv_Inn	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	.106**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.01	
	Sum of squares and Gross Products	25.120	118.132
	Covariance	3.117	9.271
	N	100	100

Note: Inf_sha = Information sharing; Serv_Inn = service innovativeness; ** = correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As shown from the data analysis using a sample size of 100 on table 1.4, the relationship between information sharing and service innovativeness is strong, positive and significant. Evidence show that Pearson product correlation coefficient is .106 and the probability value less than the critical value (i.e. $r = .106$, $p = .01 = 0.01$). In other words, information sharing is positively correlated with service innovativeness. This means, if deposit money bank employees increase their level of information sharing, service innovativeness will increase also. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between information sharing and service innovativeness was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between information sharing and service innovativeness was accepted.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The interpretation of fieldwork compared to what has been done by other researchers on these study variables. The study adopted or made use of the bivariate statistical methods in investigating the relationship between information sharing and organizational innovativeness of deposit money banks in Nigeria. However, from the statistics above, the findings revealed that there is a significant and positive relationship between information sharing and organizational innovativeness using the Pearson's product moment correlation co-efficient tool.

Here, this study is in agreement with the study conducted by Adnan et al. (2014) investigated the Effects of Managerial empowerment Applications on Organisational Creativity and Innovativeness in Enterprises: The Case of Oiz In Turkey. The study adopted a survey technique research design. Surveys that are prepared to collect information about managerial empowerment applications, creativity and innovativeness include 4 parts and 54 questions. In the first part, there are 3 questions to identify demographic information of participants. Results show that enterprises which employ managerial empowerment applications increase their organisational creativity and innovativeness at the same time. However, this depends on having a common point of view of managers and other employees in the point of expected aims and benefits.

The study is also in-line with a study conducted by Chang and Liu (2008), Titled: Managerial empowerment, innovative behavior and job productivity of public health nurses in Taiwan. The study conducted a cross-sectional research design. The objective of this study was to investigate the relationships between managerial empowerment, innovative behaviours and job productivity of public

health nurses (PHNs). Purposive sampling was conducted from six health bureaus in northern Taiwan. 670 PHNs were approached and 576 valid questionnaires were collected, with a response rate of 85.9%. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data by post. The result of the study showed that meaning and competence subscales of psychological empowerment, information and opportunity subscales of organisational empowerment, and innovative behaviours were the predictors of job productivity, only accounting for 16.4% of the variance. The competence subscale of psychological empowerment made the most contribution to job productivity ($b = 0.31$). Meaning subscale of psychological empowerment has a negative impact on job productivity. The study concluded that managerial empowerment and innovative behaviour of PHNs have little influence on job productivity. Employees with greater competence for delivering public health showed higher self-evaluated job productivity. The negative influences on job productivity possibly caused by conflict meaning on public health among PHNs in current public health policy.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the research interest and the empirical findings of the present research, its conclusion is drawn from extant literature and based on the present findings. Thus, the study concludes that; adequate information sharing and dissemination by bank managers improves both product, process and service innovativeness thereby promoting growth and expansion of deposit money banks. Managerial empowerment as a psychological construct improves organisational construct in deposit money banks thereby improving company growth, efficiency innovativeness. Based on the study findings; the following recommendations were made;

1. All deposit money banks are encouraged to engage in managerial empowerment practices such as information sharing, competence acquisition and full grant of work discretion as a means of improving organisational innovativeness.
2. Management of deposit money banks should encourage information sharing, competence acquisition and work discretion for managerial empowerment.
3. Management of deposit money banks should inculcate proper information sharing channels among their employees to guarantee product, process and service effectiveness through innovative decision and actions.

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